

EFFECT OF INNOVATION AGILITY AND STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT AGILITY ON ORGANIZATIONAL AGILITY IN HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY OF THAILAND

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Abstract

Organizational agility is vital phenomenon among the organizations which has important role in business activities. However, achievement in organizational agility is not easy and require various strategies. Particularly, it is one of the challenges in hospitality industry. Thus, the objective of this study is to identify the factors influencing organizational agility. Organizational agility is considered in relation to the hospitality industry of Thailand; therefore, population of the study is the hotels working in Thailand. Questionnaire survey is preferred and 5-point Likert scale is used for data collection. 225 responses are used in data analysis. Results of the study reported that innovation agility and strategic management agility is important to promote organizational agility. Both these factors have influence to enhance customer attraction which further lead to the higher organizational agility. This study recommended to the hospitality industry of Thailand to promote organizational agility through innovation agility and strategic management agility.

Keywords: Innovation agility, strategic management agility, customer attraction, organizational agility, hospitality industry Thailand.

1. Introduction

In the changing business environment, the companies cannot survive without the adoption of market changes. Due to entry of new businesses in the market the rapid changes in the market are quite possible. Along with the entry of new businesses, market changes are also possible due to the innovation. As in current business environment the innovation is considered as the most influential factor for business performance (Menne et al., 2022). Furthermore, due to the implementation of new technology in the era of fourth industrial revolution the rapid changes in the market are one of the common phenomena. The adoption of these changes rapidly by the business market is quite common. In this way the adoption of these rapid changes by the business organization has key importance for the companies. In this way, organizational agility provides several benefits for the companies to adopt various market changes. The adoption of new changes in the market to capture the customers is most important and it is one of the important elements of survival in the competitive market.

However, to promote organizational agility as one of the tough challenges for the companies (Khalid, Madhakomala, & Purwana, 2020). The adoption of market changes rapidly is not easy for the companies. Most importantly, it is one of the tough tasks for the small businesses in a competitive market. Because the adoption of changes in the market by the businesses require

significant cost along with the sufficient time. For all businesses it is not possible to adopt rapid changes because it also requires innovation as well as technology implementation. Innovation requires various strategies by the companies along with resources including tangible and intangible resources. Similar with other organizations the hospitality industry of any country is also one of the important industries which faces different challenges related to the organizational agility. Hospitality industry is majorly based on the service industry which always face rapid market changes. To capture the customers, it is important to highlight organizational agility in the hospitality industry.

Similar with other country, the hospitality industry of Thailand is also a vital industry which has major contribution in service industry of Thailand (Zumitzavan & Udchachone, 2014). Along with other countries this industry also requires to adapt various changes related to the market. But it is a challenge for the hospitality industry of Thailand to adopt various changes. Hotels working in Thailand always face rapid service changes due to the competitors, therefore, it is needed for hotels to adapt these changes. But it is a difficult task and require sufficient resources.

In this way the current study focusses on those factors which has effect on organizational agility. This study proposed different factors having influence on organizational agility. The organizational agility among the hotels of Thailand can be promoted with the help of various factors; however it is important to highlight those factors which has effect to adapt various market changes. The current study proposed that agility related to the innovation can promote overall organizational agility. The innovation agility (Carmeli & Dothan, 2017; Dabić et al., 2021) may lead to the customer attraction and further lead to the organizational agility. In addition to these, strategic management agility also has influential role in organizational agility. Similar with innovation agility, the strategic management agility can also promote customer attraction and increase the organizational agility. Therefore, this study highlighted that innovation agility and strategic management agility are those factors which has influence on overall organizational agility promotion. Thus, the objective of this study is to identify the factors influencing organizational agility. Although, organizational agility is one of the important phenomena in the hospitality industry, however it is not well addressed in the literature in relation to the hospitality industry of Thailand. Most importantly customer attraction is also one of the important roles to enhance the market change adaptation by the hotel but it is not formally documented in relation to the organizational agility in the literature in relation to the hotels of Thailand.

2. Hypotheses Development

Organizational agility is described as the capability of a company to adapt various external as well as internal changes. Quickly meet customer demands along with expectations. It lead change improving culture, practices as well as outcomes. Therefore, agility is majorly based on the adoption of various market changes for the welfare of customer and to promote business success (Al-Omoush, Simón-Moya, & Sendra-García, 2020; Khalid et al., 2020; Mehdibeigi, Dehghani, & mohammad Yaghoubi, 2016; Mihardjo, Sasmoko, & Rukmana, 2019). This

activity is based on the adoption of internal as well as external changes. Both the changes adoption has significant role in any business activity. This study considered organizational agility in relation to the hotels of Thailand. Therefore, different factors are considered as independent variables and mediating variable to develop the study framework. Innovation agility is considered as independent variable. Furthermore, strategic management agility is considered as independent variable. Finally, customer attraction is considered as mediating variable. Therefore, the combined effect of innovation agility, strategic management agility and customer attraction is examined in relation to the organizational agility.

Figure 1: Study Framework

2.1 Customer Attraction

All the business organizations try to attract the customers with different strategies (Georgescu, Nistoreanu, Anghel, Negoii, & Moise, 2011; Sambo & Musundire, 2020). In service industry such as hotel also try to attract customers because the attraction of customers is important for the business activities and to capture the market share with the help of satisfying the customers. Customer attraction process is based on to provide superior quality services and the provision of customized services through different ways. It has relationship with adoption of market changes. Because customer attraction is based on to provide the customized services and while providing customized services it is important to observe the market changes. The market changes always reflect the customer preference and the adoption of these changes lead to the attraction of customers. In this way, customer attraction phenomena could be in line with the organizational agility. Therefore, customer attraction focus by the companies can promote organizational agility. As previous studies are also highlighted that in organizational agility the customers have special importance (Mehdibeigi et al., 2016; Mihardjo et al., 2019). In this way, the current study proposed that;

Hypothesis 1: Customer attraction has positive influence on organizational agility.

2.2 Innovation Agility

Innovation is one of the major sources of success among the organizations (Harel, Schwartz, & Kaufmann, 2021). The focus of companies on innovative activities is always remain on priority (Munir, Arief, Abdinagoro, & Furinto, 2022; Ong et al., 2021). Particularly, the concept of innovation agility is also most important. Innovation is the need to promote services which is also be used to accept various market-based changes. Therefore, the concept of innovation agility is related to fulfill the adoption of market changes needed with the help of innovative ideas. Innovation is the important element among the organization which could be based on process, technology or any other way and which help to reduce the cost and increase the efficiency. Innovation agility is directly linked with customers of the organization. It is also linked with the organizational agility, as the adoption of changes in the market through innovative ideas fulfill the requirement of organizational agility. Therefore, it has strong association with the organizational agility directly. To produce various products or services according to the need of the customers is also based on the adoption of market changes. It also has linked with the customer attraction and it further lead to the organizational agility. Therefore, this study proposes that innovation agility has significant role to promote customer attraction which also has significant effect to enhance organizational agility. Thus, following hypotheses are proposed;

Hypothesis 2: Innovation agility has positive influence on customer attraction.

Hypothesis 3: Innovation agility has positive influence on organizational agility.

2.3 Strategic Management Agility

The strategic management of various activities among the organizations has influence on the adoption of various changes from the market as well as internal changes. To manage the external changes, it is important for the companies to manage the internal changes of the company. The internal research and development are most important (Godil, Sharif, Ali, Ozturk, & Usman, 2021)to adapt various innovative technologies from the market. Therefore, strategic management is based on the management of various resources required (Moradi & Beigi, 2020)to adapt various external changes. In this way, strategic management has an influence on the business activities. It has direct influence on the organizational agility. The promotion of management agility and the organizations can promote organizational agility with the help of customer attraction. Along with the other factors, strategic management also has influence to attract the customers. Better management among the organizations always lead to the attraction of the customers by providing quality services. Therefore, strategic management has influence on customer attraction which causes to increase organizational agility. In this way, the above discussion shows that customer attraction is playing a role of mediating variable between strategic management agility and organizational agility. From the above discussion, it is also observed that customer attraction is playing the role of mediation between innovation agility and organizational agility. Therefore, following direct and indirect effects are proposed;

Hypothesis 4: Strategic management agility has positive influence on customer attraction.

Hypothesis 5: Strategic management agility has positive influence on organizational agility.

Hypothesis 6: Customer attraction mediates the relationship between innovation agility and organizational agility.

Hypothesis 7: Customer attraction mediates the relationship between strategic management agility and organizational agility.

3. Research Methodology

The current study is based on cross sectional research design. Number of previous authors conducted research on organizational agility along with various other factors such as innovation, strategic management and customer attraction. It is observed that most of the authors have conducted cross sectional research. In this way, this study also proposed cross sectional research design for the current study. While using a cross sectional research design, this study preferred primary data to examine the relationship between variables. Therefore, quantitative research approach is followed in this study with the help of cross-sectional research design. The questionnaire survey is most supportive to collect primary data with the help of a cross-sectional design. Therefore, the current study designed a survey questionnaire to measure the relationship between innovation agility, strategic management agility, customer attraction and organizational agility.

The questionnaire of these variables is adopted from previous studies to design a survey questionnaire. Organizational agility is addressed with the help of policy and strategies of the organization to support various changes in the market. The adoption of these changes by the organization is considered to measure organizational agility. Furthermore, this study measured customer attraction by asking various questions related to the satisfaction level of the customers and repurchase intention of the customers. As the current study is based on the hospitality industry, therefore, customer satisfaction is considered in relation to the services. Innovation agility is measured with the adoption of company by various changes related to the innovation. The intention of the company to adopt various changes with the help of implementing new innovative ideas from the market is used to measure organizational agility. In addition to this, the strategic management is measured to observe various strategies of management adopted by the companies. Finally, all the scale items are designed on 5-point Likert scale which is most supportive to address the relationship between variables with the help of collecting primary data from the respondents.

By observing the sample size of previous studies in relation to these variables the current study selected 600 sample size for this study. Simple random sampling is used to distribute the questionnaires among the respondents. Questionnaires were distributed with the help of self-visit to various hotels in Thailand and with the help of online survey. The employees working in hotels of Thailand are considered as the respondents, therefore, questionnaires were distributed among these respondents. Finally, this study collected data from 225 respondents. The other respondents were not responded to the survey; therefore, 225 responses are used in this study.

4. Data Analysis

Analysis of this study is based on the structural equation modeling (SEM). SEM is used through statistical tool namely; Smart PLS3. However, before to apply SEM on this study, the preliminary data analysis is carried out. While examining the data through preliminary data analysis, various methods were used to ensure the data quality. The screening is used in the current study and observed missing value, outlier and normality of the data. The statistics of clean data are presented in Table 1. It is observed that the current data is accurate to proceed for further analysis because there is no error in the data.

Table 1: Data Statistic

	No.	Missing	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	Excess Kurtosis	Skewness
IA1	1	0	1.959	2	1	5	0.912	1.221	1.073
IA2	2	0	2.006	2	1	5	1.189	0.976	1.33
IA3	3	0	1.787	2	1	5	0.851	2.046	1.297
IA4	4	0	1.746	2	1	5	0.877	1.964	1.371
IA5	5	0	2.071	2	1	5	1.199	0.798	1.274
IA6	6	0	1.982	2	1	5	1.063	1.675	1.378
SMA1	7	0	1.899	2	1	5	1.053	0.911	1.186
SMA2	8	0	1.976	2	1	5	1.026	1.547	1.341
SMA3	9	0	1.846	2	1	5	0.89	1.135	1.171
SMA4	10	0	2.053	2	1	5	1.078	1.037	1.207
SMA5	11	0	1.864	2	1	5	1.06	1.344	1.388
SMA6	12	0	1.935	2	1	5	1.126	1.343	1.384
SMA7	13	0	1.746	2	1	5	0.955	3.065	1.683
CA1	14	0	1.953	2	1	5	1.019	1.068	1.211
CA2	15	0	2.189	2	1	5	1.12	0.094	0.92
CA3	16	0	1.728	2	1	5	0.869	4.2	1.763
CA4	17	0	2.012	2	1	5	1.104	1.132	1.281
OA1	18	0	2.012	2	1	5	1.077	0.989	1.21
OA2	19	0	1.97	2	1	5	1.04	1.349	1.237
OA3	20	0	2.195	2	1	5	1.208	0.147	1.001
OA4	21	0	2.107	2	1	5	1.162	0.172	1.024
OA5	22	0	2.284	2	1	5	1.251	-0.562	0.711
OA6	23	0	2.278	2	1	5	1.226	-0.35	0.835

Figure 2 shows the measurement model of SEM. The measurement model is consisted of factor loadings which are shown in outer model(Hair, Hult, Ringle, Sarstedt, & Thiele, 2017; Hair et al., 2019). In outer model the factor loadings given must be above 0.5. Outer model shows that innovation agility is measured through six items and none of the items has factor loading below 0.6. Strategic management agility is measured through seven scale items and none of the scale item have factor loading below 0.6. Furthermore, customer attraction is measured with the help of four items and all the items achieved the minimum criteria of 0.5. This study addresses organizational agility through six items. It is found that none of the scale item have factor loading below 0.6. Finally, the factor loading is also given in Table 2.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Table 2: Factor Loadings, CR and AVE

Construct	Items	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
Customer Attraction	CA1	0.754	0.701	0.715	0.516
	CA2	0.784			
	CA3	0.777			
	CA4	0.527			
Innovation Agility	IA1	0.675	0.829	0.875	0.539
	IA2	0.808			
	IA3	0.654			
	IA4	0.726			
	IA5	0.77			
	IA6	0.762			
Organizational Agility	OA1	0.654	0.802	0.838	0.554
	OA2	0.788			
	OA3	0.758			
	OA4	0.817			
	OA5	0.744			
	OA6	0.692			
Strategic Management Agility	SMA1	0.699	0.801	0.878	0.509
	SMA2	0.782			
	SMA3	0.659			
	SMA4	0.745			
	SMA5	0.715			
	SMA6	0.695			
	SMA7	0.692			

Factor loadings in Table 2 shows the internal item reliability. Furthermore, to check the reliability of the data the composite reliability is also examined which is presented in Table 2. The results indicated that none of the construct in this study have composite liability below 0.7 which is minimum cut off point in this today. In addition, this study also addressed average variance extracted (AVE) to confirm the convergent validity. The AVE is presented in Table 2 which shows that customer attraction, innovation agility, organizational agility, strategic management agility and organizational agility have AVE above 0.5 which confirm the convergent validity. Finally, it is also important to confirm the discriminant validity which is reported in Table 3 with the help of cross-loadings. The criteria of discriminant validity are also fulfilled by the current study which allowed this study to proceed for further analysis.

Table 3: Cross-Loadings

	Customer Attraction	Innovation Agility	Organizational Agility	Strategic Management Agility
CA1	0.754	0.447	0.494	0.603
CA2	0.784	0.544	0.587	0.693
CA3	0.777	0.575	0.509	0.611
CA4	0.527	0.412	0.307	0.407
IA1	0.465	0.675	0.282	0.407
IA2	0.574	0.808	0.555	0.603
IA3	0.481	0.654	0.353	0.495
IA4	0.386	0.726	0.502	0.416
IA5	0.504	0.77	0.462	0.504
IA6	0.602	0.762	0.588	0.618
OA1	0.594	0.544	0.654	0.523
OA2	0.502	0.531	0.788	0.585
OA3	0.456	0.442	0.758	0.454
OA4	0.5	0.535	0.817	0.521
OA5	0.537	0.388	0.744	0.539
OA6	0.381	0.364	0.692	0.341
SMA1	0.489	0.433	0.544	0.699
SMA2	0.574	0.641	0.541	0.782
SMA3	0.537	0.351	0.458	0.659
SMA4	0.573	0.611	0.526	0.745
SMA5	0.695	0.463	0.404	0.715
SMA6	0.599	0.494	0.46	0.695
SMA7	0.613	0.494	0.45	0.692

The results of the hypotheses are based on structural model which is given in Figure 4(Khan et al., 2019). Structural model is also known as inner model. Therefore, this study observed the inner model to examine the relationship between variables. Figure 3 shows the inner model in which t-statistics are given which shows the significance of the relationship. Additionally, the beta value is given in Table 4 along with the t-value which shows the direction of the relationship. In this part of data analysis, this study considered the effect of innovation agility on customer attraction and organizational agility. The results given in Table 4 shows that organizational agility has significant relationship with innovation agility as the t-value is about 1.96. Innovation agility has significant effect on customer attraction. In addition to this, the current study examined the role of strategic management agility and customer attraction and organizational agility. Results shows that strategic management agility has significant positive effect on customer attraction. It also has significant positive effect on organizational agility. Therefore, it is reported that innovation agility and strategic management agility has positive

effect to promote organizational agility. It is also reported in that customer attractions have positive effect on organizational agility. All these results are based on direct effect which are given in Table 4.

Figure 3: Structural Model

Table 4: Direct Hypotheses Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Customer Attraction -> Organizational Agility	0.277	0.279	0.098	2.827	0.005
Innovation Agility -> Customer Attraction	0.229	0.231	0.072	3.188	0.002
Innovation Agility -> Organizational Agility	0.26	0.265	0.078	3.323	0.001
Strategic Management Agility -> Customer Attraction	0.659	0.658	0.057	11.484	0
Strategic Management Agility -> Organizational Agility	0.268	0.261	0.088	3.047	0.002

Furthermore, this study addressed the indirect effect of customer attraction in Table 5. Two indirect effects are proposed based on customer attraction. The first indirect effect of customer

attraction is considered between innovation and agility and organizational agility. Second indirect effect is considered between strategic management agility and organizational agility. Results given in Table 5 shows that customer attraction is a mediating variable between innovation agility and organizational agility as the t-value is above 1.96. In addition to this, customer attraction also mediates between strategic management agility and organizational agility

Table 5: In-Direct Hypotheses Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Strategic Management Agility -> Customer Attraction -> Organizational Agility	0.182	0.184	0.067	2.724	0.007
Innovation Agility -> Customer Attraction -> Organizational Agility	0.063	0.064	0.031	2.064	0.04

5. Conclusion

The objective of this study is to identify the factors influencing organizational agility in hospitality industry of Thailand. To achieve the study objective the hypotheses were proposed based on the literature. Results of the study provided valuable insights which has major importance for hospitality industry of Thailand in relation to the organizational agility. It is found that to promote organizational agility it is important for hotels to enhance agility in innovation. The introduction of new ideas to adopt the market changes has positive influence to enhance organizational agility. Furthermore, strategic management activities are also having influential effect on organizational agility. The changes in strategic management activities in relation to the market change is also helpful to promote overall agility in the organization. As the success of any organization is based on the adoption of various changes in the market to facilitate the customers, therefore, in hospitality industry it is important to promote organizational agility with the help of innovation as well as strategic management. Furthermore, this study also concluded that customer attraction is one of the ways to promote organizational agility. The customer attraction has positive effect on agility of the organization. Therefore, it is also needed to promote customer attraction with the help of innovation and strategic management. The ability of the hotels to promote innovation agility and strategic management agility can promote organizational agility with the help of customer attraction.

6. Implications of the Study

Theoretically the current study has implications because this study proves that customer attraction can help to promote organizational agility with the help of innovation agility and strategic management agility. Number of studies in the literature addressed these factors

however, these studies have not proved that customer attraction is a way to promote organizational agility through innovation and strategic management. Therefore, the unique contribution of the current study is providing various practical implications. According to the results of the study, it is proposed to the practitioners that innovation must be used to adopt various market changes. Furthermore, it is also proved from the results and recommended to the management of the hotels that strategic management agility should be used to enhance organizational agility. Therefore, the study provides different ways in the relation to the innovation and strategic management for the practitioners to promote organizational agility.

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